

Holistic education is the contemporary need of the time

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Abstract

We want that education by which character is formed, strength of mind is increased, the intellect is expanded and by which one can stand on one's own feet. (Swami Vivekananda Vol-5). The concept of holism refers to the idea that all the properties of a given system in any field of study cannot be determined or explained by the sum of its component parts. Instead, the system as a whole determines how its parts behave. A holistic way of thinking tries to encompass and integrate multiple layers of meaning and experience rather than defining human possibilities narrowly. Holistic education aims at the development of the 'whole' individual. It focuses on all the aspects of human development which can be listed as physical, mental, psychological, social, spiritual and aesthetic. Holistic education covers a wide range of philosophical orientations and academic practices. Its focus is on completeness, and it attempts to avoid excluding any significant aspects of the human experience. It is an eclectic and inclusive movement whose main characteristic is the idea that educational experiences foster a less materialistic and a more spiritual worldview along with more dynamic and holistic views of reality. It also proposes that educational experience promote a more balanced development of – and cultivate the relationship among – the different aspects of the individual (intellectual, physical, spiritual, emotional, social and Aesthetic), as well as the relationships between the individual and other people, the individual and natural environment, the inner- self of students and external world, emotion and reason, different discipline of knowledge and different structure of knowing. Over the ages great educators and philosophers have focused on the development of the child. Educators have suggested their views on the development of his physical, emotional, intellectual, social, creative or intuitive, aesthetic and spiritual potentials.

Keywords: *Holistic education, physical, mental, spiritual, aesthetic, social.*

Introduction:

“The highest education is that which does not merely give us information but makes our life in harmony with all existence”

Rabindranath Tagore

The twenty-first century is the era of rapid change. It is the age of

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globalization, Deculturalisation, desocialisation and at the most dehumanization. This change has some subtle, but more difficult to solve side effects. First, it leads to a generalized stress on individuals, organizations and societies, that is often accompanied by information overload. The ever more rapid evolution of ideas, theories, cultures and ideologies leads to a general fragmentation of knowledge, which is sometimes described as the postmodern condition. A more dangerous result of this evolution is the fragmentation and erosion of value systems, making it more difficult for people to distinguish between good and evil, or to choose clear goals for themselves. This makes it necessary to instill in the child the values of right and wrong, to build his character in order to live harmoniously with the environment.

If we evaluate modern education, its chief outcomes can easily be identified as aggressive competition, pride and envy. At its best, the modern educational system imparts some professional knowledge and skills, but it lacks any cultivation of heart. The result is only to make the students conceited materialists. Consequently, at an age when children should be dreaming of beauty, greatness and perfection, they now dream about sensory titillation and wealth, and spend time worrying about how to earn money. No wonder that our society today is being devoured by the twin devils of acquisitiveness and unabashed consumerism, with the resultant serious social problems of corruption, strife and violence; and ecological problems such as environmental pollution and the rapid depletion of resources which threaten the very survival of humankind on this planet. Thinkers and philosophers of all hues, whether in India or abroad, agree that a complete revamping of the educational system is a prerequisite for the solution to these serious maladies besieging mankind. For, unless human beings become harmonized within themselves, through a fundamental change in their animal instincts-which should be the most important purpose of education-all changes in their outer circumstances, will ultimately be overwhelmed by their instinctual, animal brutality.

Why holistic education

Holistic education is a philosophy of education based on the premise that each person finds identity, meaning, and purpose in life through connections to the community, to the natural world, and to spiritual values such as compassion and peace. (Miller, R.1997).

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It is based on the philosophy of 'holism'. It involves the integration of multiple layers of meaning and experience through direct engagement with the environment. Holistic education is more concerned with drawing forth the latent capacities and sensitivities of the soul than with stuffing passive young minds with predigested information. It is an education that prepares young people to live purposefully, creatively, and morally in a complex world.

To understand the meaning of holistic education, we need to recognize two principles. Firstly, an education that connects the person to the world must start with the person—not some abstract image of the human being, but with the unique, living, breathing boy or girl, young man or woman (or mature person, for that matter) who is in the teacher's presence. Each person is a dynamic constellation of experiences, feelings, ideas, dreams, fears, and hopes. Secondly, we must respond to the learner with an open, inquisitive mind and a sensitive understanding of the world he or she is growing into (Miller, R. 1997).

Some advocates of holistic education claim that views central to it are not new but are, in fact, timeless and found in the sense of wholeness in humanity's religious impetus and inspiration from great philosophers, both eastern and western. In fact, the principles and practices of holistic education are already used by a number of institutions that are dissatisfied with traditional education, but they may be unaware of any critical theory about holistic education. A holistic education is usually characterized by several core qualities.

There is concern for the interior life, for the feelings, aspirations, ideas and questions that each student brings to the learning process. Education is no longer viewed as the transmission of information; instead it is a journey inward as well as outward into the world.

Holistic education expresses an ecological consciousness; it recognizes that everything in the world exists in context. This involves a deep respect for the integrity of the biosphere, if not a sense of reverence for nature.

It is a worldview that embraces diversity, both natural and cultural. It shuns ideology, categorization, and fixed answers, and instead appreciates the flowing interrelatedness of all life. It is an education that recognizes the innate potential of every student for intelligent and creative thinking. It is

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child-honoring education, because it respects the creative impulses at work within the unfolding child as much as, if not more than, the cultural imperatives that conventional schooling seeks to overlay onto the growing personality.

Thus, holistic education is essentially a democratic education, concerned with both individual freedom and social responsibility. It is education for a culture of peace, for sustainability and ecological literacy, and for the development of humanity's inherent morality and spirituality.

Aspects of Holistic Education

Holistic education aims at the development of the 'whole' individual. It focuses on all the aspects of human development which can be listed as under mentioned:

Physical – Holistic education believes that “a healthy mind resides in a healthy body”. A child should be physically sound and mentally agile to accept whatever he learns from the environment.

Mental – Self-control and self-discipline comes from the control on one's mental faculty. Holistic Education believes in training the mind and building a balanced personality.

Psychological – Development of the consciousness is another aspect.

Social - Man is a social animal. He has to live in harmony with nature. He cannot exclude himself from the environment. Thus he should learn to be a harmonious social being.

Spiritual – Man must be liberated from the bondages of desires, sufferings, ignorance, and all the evils of the society. This can only be done through illuminating the spirit.

Aesthetic – Man is the best creation of the creator. The world around has been created for him. So man must learn to respect and appreciate the Mystery and beauty around.

Holistic education in the classroom

Holistic education in the classroom is often seen as a community, which is within the larger community of the school, which is within the larger community of the village, town, or city, and which is, by extension, within the larger community of humanity. How life is lived at the smallest level should reflect what is considered to be “right living” in the largest

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context. For this reason many holistic educators feel that the claims made by conventional schools to foster freedom and democracy are spurious, as most conventional schools are based on authoritarian classrooms. They feel that learning to assume responsibility, to question for oneself what is right, and to stand by one's convictions cannot be accomplished by a childhood of unquestioningly obeying rules, conforming to codes of behaviour that seem meaningless, and believing that the authorities have the answers. Holistic educators feel that schools must be places where the relationships we want as adults exist for the students as much as possible - where open, honest and respectful communication is the norm; where differences between people are appreciated; where interaction is based on mutual support and not on competition and hierarchy; where the common weal is the responsibility of each individual; and where the decision making process (if not engaged in by everyone at some level) is at least accepted by everyone. This emphasis on co-operation rather than competition often results in holistic schools giving no grades or rewards. In this view of human nature, people are seen as being more fulfilled from nurturing and helping one another than from being placed above or below one another, and competition is seen not as producing excellence but anxiety, aggression, self-centredness, low self esteem or inflated self images. Relationships between students, between teachers, and between students and teachers are seen as both a primary source of education and a topic of education. As a source, relationships are an excellent mirror in which to see ourselves - we can learn a great deal about ourselves by seeing how others respond to us. As a topic, learning about healthy mutually sustaining relationships - how to create them and sustain them - is seen as necessary to solve many of our social and personal ills.

In holistic education practicing schools every child is seen as an expression of, an arena for, or an entity containing the transcendent, and is recognised and treated as such. Many holistic educators expressed that the sacredness inherent in each child was not just something for the educator to be aware of, it was something that each child should discover. This led many to feel that education was only partly a process of instilling or pouring in - it needed to be mostly a process of unfolding, a leading out or bringing out. If education is a process of discovery and uncovering, and every child is unique; how could the traditional educational judging of children be anything other than inherently wrong? How could a child be a

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slow learner if he was learning at a pace that was right for her/him? How could a child be disruptive if (s)he was doing what (s)he was interested in rather than what others wanted her/him to do, or were those others not in fact disrupting the child? If a child doesn't learn through words and numbers, is that child unintelligent or can that child be learning through other intelligences? In this, the work of Howard Gardner gives form and legitimacy to what many educators felt - that some children who are poor at words and numbers are nevertheless geniuses and terribly short changed, if not brutalised, by traditional education. Gardner demonstrates that learning takes place in many capacities of the child, not just the verbal-numerical capacities; and that this learning process is different for everyone - echoing two themes in holistic education and the holistic view of human nature. Many people feel it is not just a matter of valuing everyone, it is also important to value the different capacities that we all have; to do otherwise is to denigrate some individuals and to denigrate some aspects of each one of us.

Teachers, who favoured holistic education, took pride in developing new methods that reflected their new views of what a child is. Research with individual learning styles, co-operative learning, critical thinking, cross disciplinary curricula and multiple intelligence theory have inspired many new initiatives in holistic classrooms. The teacher became less of an authority who directed and controlled and was more of a friend, a mentor, a facilitator, or an experienced travelling companion. Goethe's quote, "You only learn from someone you love," becomes almost a slogan.

An ideal structure of a holistic school

A holistic education practicing school should be enriched with varied practices that develop the physical, mental, psychological, social, aesthetic and spiritual aspects of the learners. As Krishnamurti(1953) says that 'education is not merely a matter of training the mind.' (p.13) therefore 'to bring about right education, we must obviously understand the meaning of life as a whole, for that we have to be able to think , not consistently, but directly and truly..... To understand life is to understand ourselves and that is both the beginning and the end of education'(p.14). Thus the purpose of education is not only the acquisition of knowledge and facts but also realising the significance of life as a whole.

Therefore a school providing holistic education should have practices

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that will help the child realise the significance of life. The child should be able to develop into a physically, mentally, psychologically, socially, aesthetically and spiritually matured human being. The following practices can be included in the school curriculum for the holistic development of the children.

For Physical Development

A healthy body houses a healthy mind. To keep the child mentally and emotionally stable it is very necessary to develop the physical and intellectual capacities of the learners. In the words of Aurobindo, "Health and strength are the first conditions for the natural perfection of the body, not only muscular strength and the solid strength of the limbs and physical stamina, but the finer, alert and plastic and adaptable force which our nervous and subtle physical parts can put into the activities frame". "Among the natural qualities and powers of the body which can be thus awakened, stimulated and trained to a normal activity we must reckon dexterity and stability in all kinds of physical action(such as swiftness in the race, dexterity in combat, skill and endurance of the mountaineer , the constant and often extraordinary response to all that can be demanded of the soldier, sailor , traveller, explorer....)In some of them a training for common action, combined movement, discipline are needed and for that our physical exercises can make one ready..."

The school should expose the children to various physical activities like yoga,sports and games, martial art, athletics, dance and theatre. Each part of the human body needs to be developed and trained. As the Mother indicates: "The education of the body has three principal aspects:

- (a) Control and discipline of functions.
- (b) a total methodical and harmonious development of all the parts and movement of the body and
- (c) rectification of defects and deformities, if there be any." (Pani. 2012. p.300).

Howard Gardner (1983) stated that bodily-kinesthetic intelligence involves the ability to use the body to complete complex and/or intricate physical tasks. Blumenfeld-Janes (2009) defined bodily-kinesthetic intelligence as an ability to be aware of one's body in space and motion. Visser, Ashton, and Vernon (2008) showed that bodily-kinesthetic

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intelligence was often differentiated into two components: (1) gross motor ability (e.g., extraordinary balance and coordination), and (2) fine motor ability (e.g., dexterity). As bodily-kinesthetic intelligence is actualized into competence, there are also two categories: basic and advanced. Basic physical competence is often measured in terms of (1) cardiovascular endurance, (2) muscular strength, (3) muscular endurance, and (4) flexibility (Caldwell, & Huitt, 2004) while more advanced competencies are shown in such activities as dance, theatre, and sports (Visser et al.).

Nutrition and physical exercise are the two primary influences on physical development, including health and well-being (Cooper, 1999). For schools who desire to promote physical competence, it can be done by connecting academic lessons to physical education activities (Huitt, 2009b), involving children and youth in dance, theatre, or sports, or through movement education. Kogan (2004) created a movement education curriculum for elementary students; Carter, Wiecha, Peterson, Nobrega, and Gortmaker (2007) provided a similar approach for middle school students. While there can be specific advantages in having students involved in dance, theatre, sports, or movement education, the most important goal should be to have children develop strong and healthy bodies so that they can use whatever bodily-kinesthetic intelligence they possess.

For Mental Development

The mental education of the child begins with the proper training of the main organs of perception - the eyes, the ears, and the nose. This will facilitate the faculty of observation which in turn depends on concentration. Concentration depends on interest and attention of the child. To develop these faculties, learning should be associated with pleasant experiences leading to favourable attitudes (Pani, 2012, p. 367). Along with concentration, attention and observation, the other faculties that should be developed are the power of judgment, intelligence, memory and imagination. Various activities and teaching strategies involving comparison and differences of various objects example finding the difference and similarities between whole numbers and real numbers etc. can be planned for the mental development of the child. Asking analytical questions or observing various objects will enhance these faculties of the child. Co scholastic activities like quiz, debate, elocution, extempore and

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other literary activities foster the mental development of the child. Various literary and creative activities like participation in art and craft exhibitions, science exhibition etc. can help increase the imagination faculty of the child.

For Psychological Development

Psychological development can be expressed as the development of the understanding, emotions and mind of the learner. Hurlock explains understanding as “the activity to achieve a grasp of the nature, significance or explanation of something or to have a clear or complete idea of it. In short, it means the ability to comprehend. Understanding is achieved by applying previously acquired knowledge to new experiences and situations”. Understanding or cognition is a mental activity which depends on the maturation and learning of the learner. Maturation provides a state of readiness for understanding. The mental education of the child can begin with the proper training in the adequate and accurate use of the main organs of perception- the eyes, the ears, the nose and touch. This will facilitate the development of the faculty of observation. This power of observation can be developed by various strategies like experienced based learning where the children are exposed to real life situations and asked to note and observe and give their views on them. For example a child may be seeing a tree everyday, s/he can be asked to touch and feel its different parts, observe and write about it, label the different parts and its flowers fragrance can be smelt, the beauty of its contours, shade, texture can be touched and its peculiarities can be studied and described. The flower can then be dissected and its inner parts can be observed and studied. This activity will not only create interest in the children, but also it will enhance the attention span, concentration and observation power through the training of all the senses.

Associating the children with various situations and asking various open ended questions helps develop the emotions of the children. Practices like helping the poor. Collecting money and providing help to the underprivileged or needy, schools can adopt small villages to help the people there in various ways, celebrating father’s day, mother’s day, grandparent’s day in school helps in the emotional development of the child. Schools conducting and allowing students to participate in various competitions like quiz, olympiads, mock united nations, debate competitions, various exhibitions like science and mathematics etc. will

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facilitate the mental faculties of the learners. Experimentation and exploration also will enhance the creativity and imagination of the child. Various activities like planning and preparing activities to investigate certain issues will foster creativity among the children.

For Aesthetic development

The world is a beautiful place created by the Almighty for man to enjoy and appreciate. Defining aesthetic can be quite difficult as the term used can result in different definition. To put it simple, aesthetic involves the love and pursuit of beauty as found in art, movement, music and life as defined by Schirrmacher, (1998, p.222), Feeney and Moravcik (1987, p. 217) define aesthetic as ‘the awareness and appreciation of pleasant sensory experiences’ and they further refine it by stating it as ‘the ability to critically evaluate works of art according to criteria that are defined by the culture’.

The importance is viewed as a necessary component to be included in developing a child holistically in child development. Children who are exposed to beauty experiences will develop the skill to appreciate things that are taught to them in their early elementary level. This development will ultimately lead to the appreciation and valuing of good design in their adulthood. At the same time, the concept development they acquire during the process enable them to have the ability to problem solve that involves thinking and imagining.

As mentioned by Jalongo& Stamp (1997,p. 223), aesthetic education in early childhood is to create opportunities to experience and promote interest so as to lean to appreciate and develop the skill to evaluate art forms. Art helps people to understand about other cultures and examples has evidently shown that some of the information and knowledge we acquire about people from the past centuries were not recorded in the form of written words but rather in the form of drawing. The National Art Education Association (NAEA,p.15) also supported that arts is the richest sources for understanding culture as it reveals the human activities most of the time.

Aesthetic responses lie at the heart of many daily events. Children’s develop aesthetic awareness if they are surrounded by beautiful environment and experiences. Under such circumstances, the stress level is reduced and subsequently leads to positive behaviour. The exposure of beauty in nature for art experiences encourage children to express their thoughts freely as well as observing the surrounding without obstruction or

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hindrance. Therefore they can enjoy and at the same time make connection to the environment as well as appreciate their art as suggested by Friedman (2005, p.225)

Alvino(2000)highlighted that arts allows children to enjoy success as it develop children's skills in eye-hand coordination, persistent, patience and good working habits. Besides visual arts, performing together during music, dance or drama also gives children the opportunities to develop social skills as they work together as a team cooperatively.

It is found that learning in other domains also takes place through art activities. Through art education, children acquire knowledge, understanding and skills that help them in the development of physical, intellectual, emotional and social domains (PIES). Other educational experts and researchers also looked into the theoretical perspectives of various children's development by different theorists and how arts can influence and contribute to their development.

The theories of Piaget discuss about children's intellectual development and his interest in finding out how human being construct knowledge. He believes that children built up their knowledge through various stages. The first stage being the sensory motor stage whereby the children based on their senses to learn and develop about concepts through exploration and exposure to new experiences. The next stage is viewed as pre-operational stage where the children use his/her past experiences to imagine as representations of objects. Each time, as they explore and experience, they start to find meaning in their representations and by doing so, they build-up their knowledge. During this stage, children also develop their linguistic abilities by using words as substitutes for objects.

The third stage is known as the concrete operational stage whereby the children are equipped with the abilities to classify objects, recognizes difference as well as able to reason about relationship between objects.

The theories of Vygotsky focuses on social interaction of the children. Vygotsky believes that children learn best in an environment which provide opportunities for social interaction among the children. If they are engaged in activities they are comfortable with, it will motivate them to explore and learn more and thus build up their confidence. Through constant interaction between children and adults, children's intellectual development is

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enhanced as they develop new concepts, skills and competencies (Edwards 2002, p.25)

Erikson's theory of emotional and social development discussed about the social behaviour of a child at different age group and how the child responded to the people around them.

Howard Gardner's theory is one of the many theories that help us to understand the different forms of intelligence present in the human being. Gardner defines intelligence as the ability in problem solving and fashioning products. The eight intelligences he suggested are - musical, bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, spatial, linguistic, intrapersonal, logical-mathematical and naturalistic. Each of the intelligences works differently from another. By getting involved in an activity, several intelligences can be revealed at the same time.

Having discussed briefly the point of views on the different aspect of development by the various theorists, the other areas to look at is how art influences children's learning under the domains that mentioned earlier as well as what educators can do to enhance learning. In order for the educators to apply the strategies effectively, it is crucial for the educators to understand the theories and to assess the impact on children's learning. With little background knowledge, educators can find it difficult to apply the various approaches in teaching arts. By understanding why art is important for young children, educators will find it more easy and willing to see new things and adopt changes. Wright (2003, p.153) pointed out that seeing new thing allows improvement in practices through constant exploration. However, that does not mean that the existing thinking or concepts are completely removed but rather it helps to make those thinking and concepts better.

The way children and arts are viewed are equally important to the educators in their teaching. How children are perceived is affected by certain circumstances and each one is different each time by the teaching methods as well as the views on art. On the other hand, craft and other activities like singing, performing arts, drama, excursions and picnics also help in the aesthetic development of the child.

For Spiritual Development

Spiritual education consists in becoming conscious of the presence of the

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spiritual being presiding over all the phenomenal life of the individual and generating an intense seeking to be in union with the infinite and the eternal, the supreme reality.

Spiritual education begins with spiritual transformation that is the opening of the human vision and ascent of the mind in to the higher plane of the pure self-silent tranquil, illimitable. This ascent brings in an increasing inflow of the higher consciousness into lower, finally the transformation culminates in the consciousness fixing itself on this higher plane and governing the mind, the life and body from above (Pani, 2012, p. 398).

Prayer and meditation, contemplation and concentration, reading and discussion on spiritual literature and lives of spiritual leaders and spiritual practices, emulating the examples of great men, yoga, celebration of different festivals, knowing their importance and practice of other such activities leads to spiritual development.

For Social development

Man, according to Sri Aurobindo, is a developing being and education accordingly is a process of development. And development includes all the aspects of human personality, and thus it includes all the aspects of human personality, and thus it includes social development as well.

A human child is born into a society, and his development takes place in the society, never out of it or away from it and social development implies how much an individual is successful in adjusting his own behaviour in relation to behavior of others. Social development is thus a process of social interaction and education of a social process.

A human child, when grown up, is required to play many roles. He/she has to learn to be a father or a mother, a school teacher or an administrator, a priest or a shopkeeper, a politician or a social reformer. He has also to learn to obey the laws, to understand how they govern the society and to be prepared to change the social mores and when necessary. Thus it can be seen that education is the preparation of people to fit them in to the complex social structure and to enable them to play particular social roles as members of different groups. The success of life lies in playing these roles effectively.

This role play involves social interaction which implies the relation between persons and groups and resulting in the change of behaviour of the

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participants. Social interaction helps children to acquire the culture of the group. It is to be noted that all social interaction cannot come under the purview of education, but those which result in the change in behavior of the participants in the desired direction can be considered as a part of education. In this sense as well education is a social process. The school acts as a small unit of a wider society.

Social skills are skills that we need when interacting with others. There are certain ways we all must behave if we want to live a happy and a peaceful life and to have others being around us. For example, we must take turns, share, be patient, be respectful, listen, talk positive about others and be friendly. Interacting with people who do not use social skill is difficult. A person, who does not share, gets upset easily and refuses to play by the rules. He is liked by none. An important key to well-being is being involved in activities that facilitate social skills. These activities are based on doing things with others. Social skill development activities include spending time with friends, working together in groups, being involved in team sports, being a member of a club, going to different places like orphanages, old age homes, neighbourhood areas etc , writing a letter to someone or even phoning a friend or family member.

Conclusion

It is to be noted here that, though the different curricular subjects are being shown under different aspects of holistic education, their contributions are not confined to the aspects in which they are shown, for example, though science has been shown under physical development, it has immense contribution towards mental development as well. Similarly the activities brought under physical education has immense contribution towards the development of all the aspects of human personality. Thus, it can be indicated that each and every subject has some contribution towards the development of different aspects of the human personality. What is more important is that the teacher treats the subject having the objective in his or her view.

Classes in holistic schools should be often small, mixed-ability, mixed-age, and extremely flexible. If it becomes appropriate for a child to move to a different class, (s)he should move – regardless of the time of year or the subjects (s)he has been studying. Rigid categorisation by age and progression in large groups up some educational ladder should be seen as a

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reflection of the manufacturing thinking of the industrial revolution when public schooling began, and not as a reflection of new thinking about human nature. Aesthetic is connected with beauty and the study of beauty. It can stimulate children's senses in the form of art, music, dance and drama. A stimulating environment created for such activities will enhance children's learning and thinking. Development of children's creativity within a rich learning environment is further enhanced if they are supported by responsive and observant teachers. Providing opportunities to express their thoughts, ideas and feeling freely through art, music and drama not only enables the children to express things creatively, it also fosters the development of other domains such as physical, cognitive, language and social. These developments underpin the strategies used by the teachers in their planning and teaching in class.

A holistic approach in education will enable us to learn in life to discriminate between serious and trivial, the permanent and the impermanent, the full and the empty occupations, and employ our precious life span in seeking and striving to acquire the lasting, the full contentment and the glory of humanity. A programme of holistic education aims to encompass all aspects of personal learning and growth and emphasizes the development of active relationships at all levels, whether these are between the subject domains, between individuals and their peer groups and communities or between the individual and the world around them. Miller (1991, p. 3) has proposed that education may be described as holistic when it exemplifies the following characteristics:

- Holistic education nurtures the broad development of the students and focuses on their intellectual, emotional, social, physical, creative or intuitive, aesthetic and spiritual potentials.
- It promotes the importance of relationships at all levels within a learning community in which the educator and student work together in an open and collaborative relationship.
- There is an emphasis on life experience and learning beyond the confines of the classroom and the formal educational environment towards education as growth, discovery and a broadening of horizons. It encourages a desire to elicit meaning and understanding and to engage with the world.
- The approach empowers learners to examine critically the cultural, moral

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and political contexts of their lives. It leads learners towards actively challenging and changing cultural values to meet human needs..

Holistic education has the capacity to lead the students into new areas of thinking, to broaden their personal and critical thinking and develop an appreciation of the world around them, and to realize the importance that relationships have within all these considerations. Importantly, holistic education has the capacity to empower students to think differently, to think creatively and reflect on their own values.

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